

Relationship Between Secondary School Students' Study Behaviour and their Academic Achievement in Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between students' study behaviour and their academic achievement in Aboh Mbaise Local Government Area of Imo State. The researchers employed a correlation design for the study. Two research questions guided the study, and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study was six thousand, eight hundred and seventy-two (6872) senior secondary school two (SS2) students from twenty three (23) public secondary schools in Aboh Mbaise. Simple random sampling was used to select six hundred and eighty-seven (687) students who served as sample for the study. The instrument used for data collection was Study Behaviour Inventory (SBI) developed by Leonard Bliss in (1993). The researchers employed face to face method in the administration of the instrument. Data collected for the research questions were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r), while data relating to the null hypotheses were analysed by comparing the already established relationship index against the critical values at 0.5 level of significance. The findings of the study included: that there is significantly high positive relationship between the students' study behaviours and their academic achievements in both English Language and Mathematics. Based on the findings, the researchers made recommendations among which are that counsellors and teachers should try to create programmes that will help to instill and maintain good study behaviours among students so as to boost their academic achievement.

Key words: Study Behaviour, achievement, relationship, Imo State

Introduction

Unlike other animals, man is endowed with a special ability to learn so as to adapt to his complex environment. This high ability of man to learn is what distinguishes man from other animals and earns man the name - "higher animal". Learning on its own has often been described as a relatively permanent change in behaviour which results from experience and practice. This line of definition signifies that learning cannot take place without a learner. This therefore makes it very obvious that students are at the epicenter of teaching and learning process. Since students

occupy a very significant position in teaching and learning, the kind of behaviour they exhibit toward their studies greatly determines their level of academic achievement.

Consequently, in order to succeed academically, students need to demonstrate appropriate behaviours toward their studies. Moreso, it is very important that students be able to direct and control their actions in the learning process. Undoubtedly, as students regulate their own thinking, motivation, and behaviours, they initiate and sustain an active learning process which consequently leads to better academic achievements and performances. Study behaviour may be simply defined as the kind of behavior students exhibit toward their studies. Study behaviours are those actions that students carry out when they are engaged in preparation for academic tasks (Bliss & Mueller, 1993). According to Mendezabal (2013), Study behaviour is the pattern of behaviour adopted by students in the pursuit of their studies that serves as the vehicle of learning. It determines the degree and effort to which students engage in regular acts of studying. Bliss and Sandiford (2004) defined study behaviour as the typical behaviours students exhibit when they are studying.

In the context of this study, study behaviour is defined as students' manner and level of efforts directed towards their studies. Study behaviour encompasses those actions that students carry out when preparation for their academic tasks. It involves the level of time, effort and attention students give in order to gain knowledge of a subject or course of study. Study behaviour represents where, how and what students actually do at the cause of their studies. Study behaviour demonstrates students' concepts of how to accomplish learning goals and the specific actions taken to reach such goals (Jones, Slate, Perez & Marini, 1996). Consequently, study behaviour could be poor or appropriate. Appropriate study behaviour contributes to students' academic success and achievement while poor study behaviour leads to students' poor academic achievement (Zimmerman, 2008). Good study behavior serves as a driving force for students to take their studies seriously and engage meaningfully in their academic activities. In the contrary, poor behavior could lead students to procrastination, laziness and lassies-fare attitude towards their studies, which could negatively affect their academic abilities and achievement.

Previous studies have shown that study behaviour is highly related to academic achievement (Yumusak, Sungur & Cakiroglu, 2007). Similarly, Nuthana and Yenagi (2009) reported that students' study behavior and their academic achievement are significantly related. In addition, appropriate study behaviour leads to positive academic achievement and performance (Kitsantas, Winsler & Huie, 2008). Moreso, Bliss and Sandiford (2004) observed that students who exhibit good study behaviour have higher academic self-efficacy and the ability to effectively management their study time, which consequently make them to achieve better. Conversely, research also has suggested that ineffective study behaviour can lead to underachievement or even academic withdrawal (Goldfinch & Hughes, 2007). Specifically, students with poor study behaviour often keep away from difficult tasks, lack persistence, and easily give up when facing obstacles while studying (Pajares, 2008). Obviously, students' study behaviour plays a significant role in their academic achievement. According to Rana and Kausar (2011), many students fail not because they are not intelligent, but because they do not take their

studies serious. Unfortunately, some students still take their studies for granted. This therefore makes it very difficult for such students to gain high academic achievement.

Academic achievement is simply defined as the level of academic success of a student in school. According to Kpolovie, Joe and Okoto (2014), academic achievement is the ability of students to study and remember facts and being able to communicate their knowledge orally or in writing form even in an examination condition. Manhood and Igbal (2015) viewed academic achievement as the educational goal that is achieved by students over a certain period. Furthermore, Steinmayr, Dinger and Spinath (2012) described academic achievement as the results of intellectual performance in schools; an education parameter which determines students' success in the school activities. Academic achievement is considered as a key criterion to judge student's total academic potentialities and capacities which are frequently measured by the examination results (Nuthana &Yenagi, 2009).It is the outcome of teaching and learning which helps to indicate the extent to which students have achieved the set goals and objectives of a particular lesson, subject or programme. Academic achievement may generally be used to determine the overall ability of students. It showcases students' overt and covert academic abilities and capabilities. Academic achievement is usually measured with valid and reliable tests. In the context of this study, academic achievement is defined as students' scholastic ability and attainment, which signifies the overall level of knowledge they have acquired in school, a subject or a learning situation.

Since students' academic achievement occupies a vital position in the educational system as well as in the learning process, it is therefore very imperative to investigate variables such as study behaviour which can influence students' academic achievement. Moreso, there is a dearth in literature on the direct relationship between the two variables in Imo state. Against this backdrop, the study was devoted to investigating the relationship between secondary school students' study behaviour and their academic achievement in Imo State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between students' study behaviour and their academic achievement in Aboh Mbaise Local Government Area of Imo State. Specifically, the study was set out to determine the:

1. Relationship between secondary school students' study behaviour and their academic achievement in English Language.
2. Relationship between secondary school students' study behaviour and their academic achievement in Mathematics.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- What is the relationship between secondary school students' study behaviour and their academic achievement in English Language?
- What is the relationship between secondary school students' study behaviour and their academic achievement in Mathematics?

Hypotheses

The following Null Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- There is no significant relationship between secondary school students' study behaviour and their achievement in English language.
- There is no significant relationship between secondary school students' study behaviour and their achievement in Mathematics.

Method

The study adopted the correlation research design. According to Egereonu (2004), correlation studies expresses in mathematical terms the degree of relationship between two or more variables. The study was carried out in Aboh Mbaise Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria. The population was made up of 6872 (SS2) students of all the 23 public secondary schools in Aboh Mbaise as at 2016/2017 (Imo State Secondary Education Management Board, IMSEMB). The sample of the study was six hundred and eighty-seven (687) senior secondary school two (SS2) students, selected through simple random sampling.

The instrument used for measurement of student's study behaviour was Study Behaviour Inventory (SBI) developed by Leonard Bliss in (1993). The Study Behaviour Inventory composed of 46 statements to which subjects responded on a four-point scale indicating how often a particular statement might apply to them. Specifically, the response choices were (1) *Rarely or never*, (2) *Sometimes*, (3) *Often or usually*, or (4) *Always or almost always*. The instrument had a reliability coefficient of 0.86, 0.82, and 0.70 Cronbach's alpha for the scores on the three factors. Secondly, the students' scores in the two major compulsory subjects (English language and Mathematics) of the previous promotion examinations were used to represent their academic achievement scores. The administration of the instrument was carried out by the researchers and the subject teachers using face to face method by going to the sampled schools. The participants were instructed on how to respond to the instrument and were encouraged to be very honest as the result of the study will be used purely for academic purposes. The researchers on the spot retrieved the completed instrument from the respondents to avoid loss. Data collected for the research questions were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r), while data relating to the null hypotheses were analysed by comparing the already established relationship index against the critical values at 0.5 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Pearson r on students' study behaviour and their achievement scores in English language

Source of Variation	N	Study behaviour r	Achievements r	Remark
Study behaviour	687	1.00	0.91	VHPR
Achievements	687	0.91	1.00	

VHPR = Very High Positive Relationship

In table 1, it was observed that there was a very high positive relationship of 0.91 existing between the students' study behaviour and their achievements in English language.

Table 2: Pearson r on students' study behaviour and their achievement scores in Mathematics

Source of Variation	N	Study behaviour r	Achievements r	Remark
Study behaviour	687	1.00	0.63	HPR
Achievements	687	0.63	1.00	

HPR = High Positive Relationship

An observation of Table 2 reveals that, there was high positive relationship of 0.63 existing between the students' study behaviour and their achievements in Mathematics.

Table 3: Significant of Pearson r on the students' study behaviour and their achievements in English language using probability table of r

N	Cal. r	df	P value	Cal. P value	Remark
687	0.91	685	0.05	0.00	S

S = Significant

Table 3 shows that at 0.05 level of significance and 685df, the calculated r0.91 had pvalue 0.00 which was less than critical pvalue 0.05. Therefore the first null hypothesis was rejected. Thus the type of relationship existing between the students' study behaviour and their achievements in English language is significant.

Table 4: significant of Pearson r on the students' study behaviour and their achievements in mathematics using probability table of r

N	Cal. r	df	P value	Cal. P value	Remark
687	0.63	685	0.05	0.00	S

S = Significant

In Table 4 above, it was observed that at 0.05 level of significance and 685df, the calculated r0.63 had pvalue 0.00 which was less than critical pvalue 0.05. Therefore, the second null hypothesis was also rejected. Thus, the type of relationship existing between the students' study behaviour and their achievements in mathematics is significant.

Discussion

This study examined the relationship between students' study behaviour and their academic achievement. The results of this study revealed that there is high positive relationship between the students' study behaviours and their academic achievements both in English Language and Mathematics. Moreover, the results of the null hypotheses showed that the type of relationships existing between the students' study behaviour and their academic achievement in both English Language and Mathematics are significant. The findings of this study are in

accordance with the work of previous researchers (Kitsantas, Winsler & Huie, 2008; Nuthana & Yenagi, 2009; Yumusak, Sungur & Cakiroglu, 2007; Zimmerman, 2008).

The significant relationship that existed between the students' study behaviour and their academic achievement is not surprising as the students who have appropriate study behaviours possess higher academic self-efficacy and the ability to effectively manage their study time, which consequently make them to achieve better than their counterparts with poor study behaviour (Bliss & Sandiford, 2004). This means that students who exhibit appropriate study behaviours are more likely to record higher academic achievements. Conversely, ineffective study behaviour may lead to underachievement or even academic withdrawal (Goldfinch & Hughes, 2007). This therefore signifies that the better the behaviour students exhibit toward their studies, the more they achieve academic success. When students take their studies seriously, they become more purposeful and exert more zeal and effort in tackling academic challenges. This invariably enables them to acquire adequate skills and competencies that will lead to higher academic achievements and performances. The foregoing therefore underscores the assertion that the reason why most students fail is not because they are not intelligent, but because they do not exhibit appropriate study behaviours (Rana & Kausar, 2011). Appropriate study behaviour serves as a driving force for students to take their studies seriously and engage meaningfully in their academic activities.

In the contrary, poor behaviour may lead to procrastination, laziness and lassies-fare attitude towards their studies, which could negatively affect students' academic abilities and achievement. Based on the foregoing, it would be right to say that if adequate attempts are made to improve the study behaviour of secondary school students, their level academic achievement will also improve. Undoubtedly, this in turn will go a long way to reduce the high level of poor academic achievement among students in Imo state and Nigeria in general.

Conclusion

Based on the preceding findings of the study and discussions that followed, the researchers concluded that there exists a significantly high positive relationship between secondary school students' study behaviour and their academic achievement in Aboh Mbaise Local Government Area of Imo state, Nigeria.

Recommendations

In view of the findings of the study, it is recommended that:

1. Counsellors and teachers should try to create programmes that will help to instill and maintain good study behaviours among students so as to boost their academic achievement.
2. Both the Government and non-governmental organizations should create programmes in form of scholarships, debates, among others, that would help ignite a spark of energy among students to enable them take their studies seriously.

- School counsellors and educational psychologists should employ effective counselling intervention strategies to enhance students' study behaviours so as to enable them achieve their maximum academic potentials.

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